

SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE CRIME OF TRAFFICKING IN MINOR CHILDREN

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Abstract: V state consideration of the problem, directions and areas of prevention of criminal transactions in the Republic of Uzbekistan and ix liquidation, as well as the negotiation process in our Republic, implementation of warnings and transactions, children, existing regulations in regional mechanisms and their adoption. Suggestions and recommendations regarding legal and psychological situations are given in detail.

Key words: human trafficking, child trafficking, forced labor, crime, adoption, orphanage, guardianship and trusteeship.

Аннотация: В статье рассмотрены проблемы, возникающие в сфере предотвращения преступлений торговли детьми в Республике Узбекистан и их ликвидации, а также процесс борьбы с торговлей детьми в нашей Республике, реализуемые меры по предотвращению торговли детьми, существующие нормативные акты в в области механизмов отдачи и усыновления детей даются предложения и рекомендации относительно правовых и психологических ситуаций.

Ключевые слова: торговля людьми, торговля детьми, принудительный труд, преступность, усыновление, детский дом, опека и попечительство.

There are a number of global problems on our planet, including transnational crimes such as child trafficking. Every year the number of people suffering from this disease and becoming its victims is increasing. Each of these crimes, which know no territory or borders, poses a serious threat to the development of society and the country. Such a serious crime as child trafficking is so disgusting that it violates the life, freedom and rights of a person, tramples on his will, destiny and future. It should be said that the growth of child trafficking, that is, the use of a person as a commodity, so to speak, an object of trade, and the violation of his rights and freedoms causes the following: the illegal activity of a child, such as human trafficking becomes a source of income for groups consisting of one or more members, that is, they are trying to earn a lot of income without any hard and persistent work; in simplicity, indifference and indifference to the fate and future of persons who are victims of child trafficking. That is, because of their easy and careless attitude towards the concept of a free life, considered the highest good, these children become prey for criminals, or rather, their easy source of income; when criminals involved in child trafficking act against their friends and close relatives, i.e. gaining their trust and forcing them to become victims of child trafficking.

The fight against child trafficking in human history At the end of the 19th and beginning of the 20th centuries, there was a large-scale migration of women from Europe to the American and North African continents, and the phenomenon of women being sold to Europe was observed. To put an end to this phenomenon, two conferences were held in Paris in 1902 and 1910 and the World Convention for the Suppression of the White Slave Trade was adopted.

This convention was later supplemented by the Global Conventions “Eliminate Trafficking in Women and Children” and “Eliminate Trafficking in Adult Women”. Further historical processes to combat the problem of child trafficking developed gradually, and in 1948 the

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Universal Declaration of “Human Rights” was adopted. After this, the European Convention on Human Rights, the Slavery Convention, the Supplementary Convention for the Abolition of Slavery, the Convention on the Rights of the Child, the Convention on the Rights of Women, and the Convention against All Forms of Discrimination were adopted. accepted and used in many countries around the world.

On November 20, 1989, the Convention on the Rights of the Child was adopted, which entered into force for the Republic of Uzbekistan on July 29, 1994. In 2013, the United Nations designated July 30 as World Day against Trafficking in Persons. Currently, this type of crime, which is an integral part of transnational organized crime, is spreading throughout the world. According to the analytical conclusions of UN experts and the International Organization for Migration, the number of victims is several million. It is alarming that the majority of victims of human trafficking are women and children.

It would be wrong to consider child trafficking only as a problem of the Republic of Uzbekistan, since currently crimes related to child trafficking are widespread in many countries and are of concern to the entire world community.

The saddest thing is that crime associated with child trafficking is widespread: sections of the population in need of social protection are unemployed citizens, women experiencing many difficulties in family life, and minors left without the attention and care of their loved ones. parents or that they use it for their own selfish purposes, pretending that they are solving their problems.

A trafficker attacks victims by preventing them from exercising their rights and freedoms as reflected in the Constitution and laws. Such criminals abuse people physically, mentally and sexually, hold them by force, and neglect personal safety and a healthy lifestyle. It is very sad that these crimes mainly involve children and women. The Republic of Uzbekistan is implementing a number of measures to prevent and combat child trafficking, which is one of the most pressing problems today. At the same time, given that child trafficking is transnational, that is, a crime that does not choose territory and borders, in our country on December 12, 2003, the UN General Assembly adopted in 1950 “On the fight against the use of children and prostitution by third parties” joined to the Convention.

Convention for the Suppression of Transnational Organized Crime, adopted by the UN General Assembly on November 15, 2000, and to prevent and suppress the sale of children, especially women and children, and for this purpose the Additional Protocol on Punishment. was also ratified. Also, during the years of independence, a number of treaties and agreements were signed with foreign countries to combat organized crime, including dangerous forms of child trafficking.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Combating Trafficking in Persons” was adopted on April 17, 2008, and in order to further improve this law and adapt it to modern requirements, changes and additions were made to it. A new edition was adopted. August 17, 2020 The need to develop a new version of the law is due to the fact that today there are no specific provisions on the issues of protection and assistance to victims of child trafficking and the specifics of combating child trafficking and forced labor, including identification. The legal status of activities, assistance and protection is explained by a clear definition. Article 11 of this Law is devoted to the issue of “Assistance to children affected by human trafficking,” and it is necessary, in cooperation with all authorities, to develop precautionary measures in order to ensure the rights of children affected by human trafficking and socio-psychological protection. When placing

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children who have been victims of human trafficking in specialized institutions, it is necessary to organize psychological trainings, classes, and conversations in order to put their spiritual and mental state under the supervision of specialists, restore impaired mental processes and improve mental health. If children who are victims of human trafficking are not in the care of their parents or do not know about their family, then it is necessary to find parents or their surrogates and constantly improve the child's new situational skills, and his adaptive characteristics must be monitored. It is known that more than 9 thousand non-governmental non-profit organizations operate in our republic, about 100 of them are engaged in the fight against child trafficking. The law defines non-governmental non-profit organizations among the organizations providing assistance to government bodies carrying out activities in this direction, and clearly discloses their powers and responsibilities. At the same time, in contrast to the current Law, the new version of the Law establishes the procedure for ensuring social rehabilitation and adaptation of victims of child trafficking, the procedure for ensuring the confidentiality of information about victims, as well as security measures and other guarantees provided to them. Behind the crime of child trafficking are illegal acts such as forced labor, modern slavery, forced donation, use in military and terrorist conflicts, and forced prostitution. Every year, more than 4 million people are affected by child trafficking in more than 150 countries, 80% of them are women and children. Today, our country is carrying out systemic reforms to combat child trafficking, prevent and completely eliminate forced labor. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev emphasized that at the 46th session of the UN Human Rights Council, in cooperation with the International Labor Organization and the World Bank, effective reforms were implemented to eradicate forced and child labor. Our republic is implementing a number of practical and organizational measures to increase the effectiveness of efforts to combat child trafficking and prevent crime in this regard.

An analysis of the process of combating child trafficking in our republic, measures taken to prevent child trafficking, mechanisms for giving and adopting a child, as well as current regulatory documents in this area shows that child trafficking and the emergence of child trafficking are influenced by a number of factors. committing crimes. Firstly, the child's family is not socially protected, needs financial support, or uses financial benefits from the unborn child to hide the pregnancy of unmarried girls. Secondly, there is a great need in society for the adoption of a newborn and healthy child from childless families. Thirdly, cases of organization of trafficking in children with the aim of obtaining large financial benefits from trafficking in children. Secondly, there is a great need in society for the adoption of a newborn and healthy child from childless families. Thirdly, cases of organization of trafficking in children for the purpose of obtaining large financial benefits from trafficking in children. Fourthly, there is no effective comprehensive interdepartmental state system and a perfect regulatory framework to prevent the sale of a pregnant woman from the moment the fetus is discovered until the birth of the child. The complexity of the current adoption procedure in our country causes certain difficulties when adopting a child. One of the saddest cases is that employees of government agencies, through their illegal actions, participate in the crime of child trafficking. The main reason for this is the fact that healthcare workers receive a large financial allowance. In the course of investigations conducted by the investigative authorities, it was established that the doctors of the maternity hospitals for criminal purposes concealed the fact that the woman was pregnant, that the woman who came for the child prepared false documents about her pregnancy, or that the maternity hospital employees killed her child, additional crimes related to forgery of documents. Based on the above problems, there are a

number of systemic shortcomings in the effective functioning of mechanisms to prevent child trafficking, adoption and adoption. First of all, it is necessary to determine the social and psychological causes of these situations. First of all, there is no comprehensive system of mutual cooperation between government agencies and their work with public organizations in order to prevent and combat child trafficking. Secondly, there is a lack of knowledge and experience among relevant employees of internal affairs bodies in the early detection of crimes related to child trafficking, consideration of applications for this type of crime, investigation and referral to court. Thirdly, the reason for the growth of this type of crime is the imposition of light sentences on the perpetrators of crimes related to child trafficking, especially on intermediaries. Fourthly, the development of an automated information system for recording women of childbearing age and maintaining records from early pregnancy to the birth of a child has not been completed. Also, through this system it is impossible to identify pregnant women who have not applied to a medical facility. Fifthly, there is no effective system of interaction between general practitioners and patronage services operating in the regions to identify pregnant women and organize their medical supervision in cooperation with public gathering workers and a prevention inspector. At sixth, there is no system of transparency in the activities of guardianship and trusteeship authorities related to the adoption of a child. The abundance of documents in this process forces applicants to wait in line for years. In this regard, it is necessary to simplify the adoption procedure and ensure transparency of this process. At the same time, it is necessary to develop and approve an interdepartmental procedure for interaction with public organizations, clearly defining the tasks of each government body in the field of combating child trafficking. It would be advisable to take effective punitive measures against perpetrators of crimes related to child trafficking, especially intermediaries, and ensure the inevitability of punishment.

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